

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PRESENCE OF PATHOGENIC FUNGI IN THE MYCOBIOTA OF SUBTROPICAL FRUIT PLANTS IN THE ABSHERON REGION AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES

Jabrayilzade Sabiya

Associate Professor,

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Baku

Abstract

Various pathogenic fungal species are observed in the mycobiota of subtropical fruits grown in the Absheron region. Fungi belonging to the genera *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* cause diseases in fruits and negatively affect the quality of the product. The study examines the spread of these fungi and the development of pathologies caused by them, emphasizing the importance of phytosanitary control and preventive measures.

Keywords: Absheron, subtropical fruits, mycobiota, pathogenic fungi, fruit diseases, mycotoxins, phytotoxic effect, pathology, phytosanitary control.

The research will discuss the results of studies conducted on the distribution of pathogens recorded in dry subtropical fruit plants of Absheron and the prevalence of diseases caused by them.

Before proceeding to the explanation of the data obtained as a result of the studies conducted in this direction, it should be noted that in determining the number of pathologies, preference has been given mainly to those whose pathologies have been identified in one or another study and who have a methodical

approach to their identification (12,15, 18-22). In other words, it should be said that the results given below, primarily those related to the number of pathologies in the studied plants, should be considered as a minimum indicator of what actually exists (2,4-9).

Information on other diseases found in almonds during the research, their causative agents, and the range of disease incidence in 2024-2025 is provided in the table.

Table

Frequency of diseases observed in almonds

№	Disease	The causative agent of the disease	Frequency of occurrence (%)
1.	Moniliosis or fruit rot	<i>M. fructigena</i> <i>M.laxa</i>	6,8-10,2
2	Leaf burn	<i>P. ochraceum</i> <i>P.rubrum</i>	4,5-6,6
3	Diplodiasis	<i>D. amygdali</i>	5,7-8,1
4	Leaf rot	<i>F. pisifacia</i>	7,8-8,9
5	Fading	<i>V.albo-atrum</i>	3,7-5,3
6	Root rot	<i>F. annosa</i>	4,7-5,3
7	Stem rot	<i>F. cytisina</i> <i>F. pinicola</i>	5,9-8,7
8	Rust disease	<i>G. confusum</i> <i>T. discolor</i>	3,6-5,1
9	Phyllactinosis	<i>Ph. salmoni</i>	7,9-10,2
10	Septoria	<i>S.amygdali</i>	6,4-9,3
11	Ashing	<i>Sph. pannosa</i>	3,3-5,4
12	Gray rot	<i>B. cinerea</i>	7,2-10,1
13	Root rot	<i>Armillaria mellela</i>	10,2-13,4

It should also be noted that during the registration of diseases, sometimes one individual of the plant was simultaneously affected by one or another disease. During the course of the studies, it was not uncommon for the above diseases to be recorded in any of the almond individuals that were observed and were more than 8-10 years old, that is, in most cases, symptoms of one or another disease were observed in the individual plant Aliyeva, Yusifova, Rzayeva, Dzhabrailzade (2019). This is also confirmed by the general frequency of occurrence of diseases in relatively old individuals of the plant - 75.4% (64.3% of the total number). The most common number of diseases found together was 8 (powdery mildew, gray rot, wilting, spotting, phylactinosis, leaf burn, root rot and diploidiosis). Symptoms of these or other diseases are rare in young individuals of the plant, the quantitative expression of which is generally 3.8-5.7% (1-4,8,9).

The study was conducted on the main subtropical fruit crops cultivated in various horticultural farms of the Absheron region - pomegranate (*Punica granatum*), fig (*Ficus carica*), olive (*Olea europaea*) and almond (*Prunus dulcis*). Samples from plants and their fruits were collected during the vegetation period - at different phenological stages (during flowering, ripening and harvesting) (2,4,5). Samples for laboratory analysis were collected in sterile bags and brought to the laboratory for mycological analysis under appropriate conditions (at a temperature of 4°C). Small pieces of fruit and leaf surfaces were used with a sterile knife to isolate fungi and they were inoculated onto Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), Czapek-Dox and Sabouraud agar nutrient media. The incubation process was carried out for 7–10 days in an incubator regulated at a temperature of +25–27°C. Fungal colonies were studied under a microscope, and their identification was carried out based on their morphological and microscopic features. Fungal genera and species were identified based on the morphology of microscopic structures (conidia, conidiophore, mycelium) (4).

To study phytotoxic activity, aqueous extracts of some pathogen isolates were prepared and the effect of these extracts on various plant seeds (e.g., wheat and barley) was evaluated by bioassay method. Seed germination, root and shoot length, and color changes were observed to determine the degree of phytotoxic effect.

References

1. Aliyeva G.R., Yusifova A.A., Rzayeva A.L., Dzhabrailzade S.M. (2019). Species composition of *Trichoderma* Pers. Common for Technogenically violated Cenosis in the conditions of Azerbaijan. International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences.
2. Muradova S.M., Jabrailzade S.M. (2023). Toxic effect metabolites of micromycetes spread in Azerbaijan. Biosciences biotechnology research Asia.
3. Jabrailzade, S., & Aslanova, S. (2024). Assessment of Pathologies Caused by Anamorphous Fungi Distributed in Some Areas of Azerbaijan According to the Degree of Hazard.
4. Jabraylzadeh, S., Aslanova, S., & Ismayilova, G. (2024). GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYTOPATHOGENIC SPECIES OF FUNGAL

BIOTA OF SOME MEDICINAL PLANTS FOUND IN THE FLORA OF TALYSH (AZERBAIJAN). *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (84).

5. Gasimova, G., Sultanova, N., Muradov, P., Jabrailzade, S., & Namazov, N. (2020). Prospective uses of relict trees in the urban landscaping of Azerbaijan for resistance to fungal disease. *Revista Cubana de Ciencias Forestales*, 8(2), 231-240.

6. Yusifova, A., Aslanova, S., & Asadova, B. (2024). Mycology of Fodder Plants in Different Areas of Azerbaijan the Results of Studies Devoted to the Evaluation. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 10(10), 49-54.

7. Jabraylzade, S., & Aslanova, S. SOME DISEASES OF APPLE PLANTS OCCURRING IN THE TALYSH ZONE (AZERBAIJAN).

8. Balakhanova, G., & Aslanova, S. (2025). The main causes of pathogenic diseases in soil ecosystems by microfungi. *Nature & Science*, 7(4), 28-32.

9. Jabraylzade, S. (2025). DISEASES OF APPLE PLANTS OF THE SOUTHERN SLOPE OF THE GREAT CAUCASUS (Azerbaijan). *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (102).

10. Юсифова, А., Асланова, С., & Асадова, Б. (2025). ОЦЕНКА МИКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ КОРМОВЫХ РАСТЕНИЙ, РАСПРОСТРАНЕННЫХ В НЕКОТОРЫХ РАЙОНАХ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (99).

11. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). SPECIES COMPOSITION AND RESOURCES OF CULTIVATED AND WILD FORAGE PLANTS IN AZERBAIJAN. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift Für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, 84, 11–14.

12. Aslanova, S., & Asadova, B. (2023). Flora and fauna of Azerbaijan. *ASPU. Baku. P-347*.

13. Jabraylzade, S., & Aslanova, S. SEPTORIA DISEASE OF APPLE PLANTS OCCURRING IN THE TALYSH ZONE.

14. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). General Characteristics of Azerbaijan Forage Plants and Their Mycobiota and Mycological Safety Principles Applied During Use. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 10(8), 66-74.

15. Aslanova, S., & Safarova, A. (2025). GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MYCOBIOTA OF VEGETABLES AND MELONS CULTIVATED IN THE SOUTHERN REGION OF AZERBAIJAN. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, 11(3).

16. Гурбанов, Э., Асланов, С., & Сафарова, А. (2024). КЛИМАТИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ГОРНОЙ ЧАСТИ ТАЛЫША. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (90).

17. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2025). Evaluation of Phytopathogenic Fungi According to the Degree of Danger. *Advanced Studies in Biology*, 17(1), 27-36.
18. Юсифова, А., Асадова, Б., & Асланова, Ф. (2025). НАКОПЛЕНИЕ И ВЫНОС МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТОВ УРОЖАЕМ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ МАССЫ И ЗЕРНА КУКУРУЗЫ. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (102).
19. ДЖАБРАИЛЗАДЕ, С., & САФАРОВА, А. МИКОБИОТИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗНООБРАЗИЕ И ФИТОПАТОГЕННЫЕ ГРИБЫ ЯБЛОНЬ БОЛЬШОГО КАВКАЗА. *NORWEGIAN JOURNAL OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE*, (158), 8-11.
20. Muradov, P. Z., Gasimova, G. C., Namazov, N. R., Sultanova, N. H., & Jabrailzade, S. M. (2020). Comparative Study Of Mycobiota Of Some Relict Plants Included To The Flora Of Azerbaijan. *Journal of Complementary Medicine Research*, 11(2), 227.
21. Aliyeva, G. R., Yusifova, A. A., Rzayeva, A. L., & Jabrailzade, S. M. (2019). Species composition of Trichoderma Pers. common for Technogenically violated Cenosis in the conditions of Azerbaijan. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*.
22. Bakshaliyeva, K. F., Guliyeva, N. N., Jabrailzade, S. M., & Hashimova, P. M. (2019). Enzymatic activity of mikromycetes isolated from thermal water sources of Azerbaijan. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci*, 8(7), 2473-2477.